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Unseen Hands

I couldn't forget that very time in my life when my mother told me: "Child, obey your parents in all things for this is well-pleasing to the Lord". It was in the early days of September 1999. Why not? It's a verse from Holy Scripture, but I never perceived it to be of much value. It was not because I detested the words of God, nor did I easily shun being sermonized. It's just that I think it was because of one thing, my parents. Even I couldn't figure out why.

"Nay, I'll go with my classmates to the beach tomorrow, po. It's Saturday, there's no class," I said one morning while I was preparing for school.

"No," she answered straight away without even looking at me, and continued putting some clothes into the tub. "Nay, please..." I pleaded. "I must be there".

"Is that important, dong?" She addressed me in my Bisayan nickname. "It's to me!" I retorted.

I saw her face turn bitter. "You'll stay here tomorrow. No one will be left in the house. Your tatay and I will..."

"N-never mind, Nay, forget it!" I said, then walked out of the house, rudely slamming the door. I heard her voice yelling at me. I ran as swiftly as I could before she could render me a lengthy sermon. She didn't understand. Surely, my friends will all be angry if I am not with the group. I ran and ran, not knowing where. Then a sudden thought came to mind: My friends could get what they'd asked for from their parents. Why couldn't I? Do my parents really love me? I envied my friends. I trod the road sadly, so greatly disappointed.

Suddenly, I noticed that I was on the road I'd never taken before. Something had changed in the surroundings for just a moment. I looked around; all was new. There were no houses, and all I could see were trees and grass at both ends of the road. Am I dreaming? Or is my sight deceiving me? I rubbed my eyes. It was no dream. Now I realized...I was lost! I heard my chest throbbing rapidly like a drum. I wondered deeply why I had come to that lonely place.

"What are you looking for, friend?" asked a strange voice. I turned my back and got a sight of a thin gentleman in a tattered dress. He was smiling at me. I hadn't seen him before, and surely he didn't know me as well. "What are you looking for?" he asked for a second time. I finally managed to say something. "I-I'm lost, I don't know where I am," I stammered.

He eyed me, trying to figure out if I was really telling the truth. "You seem lost indeed," he said. "Come with me. There's no other house here". He then took the bend of the road to the left. I followed him. We came into an old hut. I was enchanted by his hospitality, which reflects the unique Filipino culture and sets it apart from all others.

